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Broadening and integrating public health supervisions in Regional Director of Health Services, Colombo

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Background: Regular and frequent supervision is crucial to ensure quality of service. Supervisory officers at medical officer of health (MOH) offices employ various supervision tools for this purpose. Though many aspects are covered by already available supervisory formats, those are not available for several service components which are novel additions.

Description of the intervention/ initiative: All existing supervision tools and those innovated at MOH level were divided into 11 categories and scrutinised over a consultative meeting at district level. Tools which require updates and revisions were identified. Areas which lacked supervision tools were identified and new tools were developed. A representative committee was appointed to refine, collate and finalise the tools after incorporating inputs from national level. All tools were printed on a proportionate basis and distributed for use from January 2025 and linked to the supervision monitoring mechanism at district level.

Methods used for evaluation: The number of supervisions completed by each supervisory officer and the category of service supervised per month was monitored.

Lessons learnt: New tools were developed for supervision of 'local conference', 'monthly conference', 'in-service' and 'weekly epidemiological review meeting'. These tools also served as meeting minutes for the same. The supervision submission rate increased from 50% in January to 62 % in February. It was observed that supervisory officers made an effort to supervise all areas within their purview using the tools. Qualitative feedback from supervisors appreciated the dual utility and structured guidance received from new tools.

Conclusion: Introducing a standardised set of supervision tools ensure that overlooked and novel service areas are appraised regularly.

Keywords: Supervision tool; medical officer of health; supervisory formats

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